

In this Issue

Milestones Accomplished in CONSENTIS	Page 1
CONSENTIS strengthens presence across Europe	Page 1
Joint Publication in IEEE CSR	Page 2
1 st General Assembly meeting in Patras	Page 2
Next face-to-face meeting	Page 2

Identity and Consent Management for EU Digital and Data Strategies

| Milestones Accomplished in CONSENTIS

Since its kickstart in November 2024, CONSENTIS has been consistently advancing. As the completion of Work Package 3, titled “Requirements and Architecture specification” is approaching, significant progress has been made for the Project.

During WP3, the consortium focused on the analysis of State-of-the-Art methods in Identity and Consent Management, relevant EU strategic initiatives and activities, legal frameworks and ethical aspects in personal data management and sharing.

The three CONSENTIS Use Cases were refined, and two questionnaires were distributed—one to Data Subjects (Users) and another to Identity and Service Providers (e.g., hospitals, insurers, IT companies). Analysis of the responses yielded several requirements for CONSENTIS. Flow diagrams were produced for each Use Case, illustrating both business and technical perspectives.

Based on these results, the consortium designed the CONSENTIS framework architecture and its building blocks, ensuring alignment with EU regulations and

specifications.

Next Steps

In the upcoming WP4 and WP5, partners will implement CONSENTIS by integrating existing tools and developing new ones within the agreed architecture to deliver a fully functional identity and consent management solution.

| CONSENTIS strengthens presence across Europe

During the last months, the CONSENTIS Project was actively represented in key dissemination events across Europe.

TILT Dept Meeting: On January 28, our partner, Tilburg University hosted a presentation of CONSENTIS on its premises during the TILT (Tilburg Institute for Law, Technology, and Society) Department Meeting.

TEDx Patras Workshop: On May 17, during TEDx Patras, UPAT hosted a workshop on privacy and security, open to all audiences. CONSENTIS was showcased along with several other exciting initiatives.

CPDP 18th IC: During 21-23 of May, Tilburg University represented CONSENTIS in the 18th CPDP (Computers, Privacy and Data Protection) International Conference, drawing attention from the academia and stakeholders.

Radio Interview: On May 23, Tilburg University gave an interview on privacy and data protection with Avatar.fm, enhancing CONSENTIS’ presence and impact across Europe.

TRUSTED Webinar: On June 19, UPAT shared a brief overview of the CONSENTIS Project during a Webinar organized by Gradient and the TRUSTED Project, exploring the topic: “How is the European Union advancing in Digital Identity and Data Privacy initiatives?”.

| Joint Publication in IEEE CSR

UPAT had the chance to represent the CONSENTIS consortium during 2025 IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience (IEEE-CSR). The conference was held in Crete, Greece during August 4-6. UPAT presented a Joint Publication titled “CONSENTIS – An Innovative Framework for Identity and Consent Management for EU Digital and Data Strategies”, that was composed with efforts from all partners, which described an overview of the Project. The paper is accessible online [here](#).

| 1st General Assembly meeting in Patras

On March 18-19, 2025, the 1st General Assembly meeting of CONSENTIS was successfully held in Patras, hosted by our partner UPAT. All partners were actively represented, contributing to constructive discussions on key elements of the project. The gathering created an excellent setting to strengthen cooperation, coordinate next steps, and ensure a shared vision. The program also included a social event, which further supported the development of strong working relationships among the partners.

| Next face-to-face meeting

The 2nd General Assembly Meeting will take place in Tilburg on October 14-15, 2025. The meeting will focus on activities carried out under the Work Package 4, titled “CONSENTIS building blocks and underlying technologies” and Work Package 5, titled “CONSENTIS framework for SSI and user-centric consent management”.

NEXT PLENARY MEETING
TO BE HELD 14-15 OCTOBER 2025
IN TILBURG NETHERLANDS
HOSTED BY TILBURG UNIVERSITY

JOIN US IN SHAPING THE FUTURE OF DIGITAL IDENTITY!

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